

Evaluating Menstrual Hygiene and Sanitation Facilities for Women Prisoners in Punjab: Compliance with Pakistan Prison Rules 1978 in the Context of the Sustainable Development Goals

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Abstract

Woman's fundamental rights are not taken away by her imprisonment. Menstruation in jail mostly turns into an unmanaged and quiet agony. This study explores Punjab prisoner women's access to menstrual hygiene and sanitation facilities, examining adhesiveness to Punjab Prison Rule 1978 and its alignment with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3, 5, 6 and 16. Thirteen female detainees were interviewed in the jails of Rawalpindi. Qualitative approach along with purposive sampling was used to choose participants, to account for differences in age and marital status. IPA method was used to analyze the written transcriptions of data, enabling for the discovery of themes and deeper meaning, Five themes emerged from the findings; 1. Lack of sanitary products and dependence on unsafe alternatives; 2. Risking health and lack of medical support; 3. Mental distress due to dishonor, stigma and neglect; 4. Institutional insensitivity such as humiliation by staff and inadequate sanitation facilities; 5. Poor diet and nutritional deficiencies that contribute to hormonal imbalance. Younger female prisoners were scared of infertility while menopausal women reported excessive bleeding which went untreated. Conditions in both prison analyzed systematic indifference to biological requirements of women. Study comes to conclusion the Punjab's jails continue to neglect seriously Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM), which is clearly against national and international jail legislation. Restoring and preserving the dignity and securing the fundamental human rights of women who are imprisoned requires immediate measures and execution as well, such as supply of sanitary products, better diet, medical attention and gender-sensitive training and personnel.

INTRODUCTION

The condition of prisons mostly reflects a government's dedication toward justice, health and human decency. In Pakistan, the prisons function not just as punitive facilities but also as the places where the treatment of prisoners is an important measure of compliance with the standards of human rights. Female prisoners compose specific vulnerable demographic within this system because their biological and specific requirements go unapprised. The human rights entities have explored the concerns in term of overcrowding, limited financial resources, improper healthcare facilities and specifically the gender insensitivity in Pakistan's punitive institutions (NCHR, 2024; Human Rights Watch, 2023). Nonetheless these understanding, menstrual hygiene and sanitation are fundamental requirements attached to the dignity and health, as continued to be markedly underexplored in policy and academic domains. The indifference for menstrual hygiene management (MHM) has immense consequence. During menstruation, the inadequate cleanliness impacts physical health and aggravate psychological stress along with social stigma. South Asian research explores that incarcerated women experiences high frequency of Urinary Tract Infections (UTIs), Reproductive Tract Infections (RTIs) and menstrual irregularities due to improper nutrition and sanitation facilities (Butt, 2014; Kausar et al, 2022). As compare to women in free countries, prisoner women are not able to depend on social networks or market address institutional deficiencies, due to which their health and dignity are completely conditional upon state's adherence to laws and international human rights promises. The study examines menstruation hygiene in the jails of Punjab within broad discussions on justice, health and sustainable development. By analyzing the issue through legal framework and observed facts, it explores

how the situations in jail serve as litmus test for Pakistan's dedication to human rights, gender equality and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Legal Framework: Pakistan Prison Rules 1978 and The International Law

The Pakistan Prison Rule 1978 was derived from the Colonial Prisons Act 1894, which contains the primary legislative and administrative foundation for the governance of prison. Particular needs of female prisoners are recognized in these rules i.e. supply of sanitary pads, soap, laundry detergent and garments especially for women. These Rules include provisions for pregnant prisoners, delivery and childcare in punitive facilities, focusing the state's obligation to confirm health and dignity of jailed female (Government of Pakistan, PPR 1978). Theoretically, these provisions are according to the constitutional provisions under Article 25, which ensures equality and Article 9, which protects the right to life and dignity. Pakistan is an endorser to the International Conventions, particularly the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW), which had obliged the states to eliminate gender-based discrimination and ensure women's access to healthcare services. United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the nursing of prisoners (Nelson Mandela Rules) and the Bangkok Rules laid down specific measures to fulfil women's cleanliness and healthcare requirement (UNODC, 2015). The inconsistency between the legislation and execution persevere significantly. The reports from Punjab Commission on Status of Women (2018) and the National Commission for Human Rights (2024) proclaim diligent deficiencies in sanitary pads, soap, clean water and expert female medical doctors in women's prisons. Moreover, the cultural dishonor linked with menstruation repels individuals from speaking grievances, which

allow the continuation of negligence. This disparity highlights the systematic deficiencies in execution. Although PPR 1978 provides progressive framework, but unfortunately improper oversight, insufficient financial resources and implanted patriarchal behavior within the prison system lead to poor compliance.

Menstrual Hygiene as a Pre-Requisite

Management of Menstrual Hygiene (MHM) is not just a question of comfort but is a basic component of women's health and dignity. Improper menstrual hygiene management is linked directly with crucial health concerns like reproductive tract infections, urinary tract infections, infertility and problems which may end up in chronic illness (Sommer et al, 2016). These issues are increased by overcrowding, unhygienic washrooms and little privacy. For imprisoned women, menstruation management is health concern and a matter of fundamental human rights. Psychological incompetency to manage menstruation with dignity can result in humiliation, shame and sadness. Study explores that females without having access to sanitary products mostly experiences taunts, humiliation and established mediocrity, exacerbating their vulnerability (Mahon & Fernandez, 2010). In prisons characterized by powerful and strict hierarchies, women mostly face humiliation or gets neglected while asking for sanitary products from staff (Kausar et al, 2022). The neglect of gendered menstruation illustrates systemic discrimination, as the biological demands of men seldom confront similar prison invisibility. The activists and scholars maintained that understanding menstruation health as rights-based challenges necessitates that state ensures access to sanitary pads, clean water, soap and privacy as fundamental right rather than luxury (Sommer et al, 2016). Menstruation hygiene is nearly associated with the principles of equality and dignity, as

constructed in The Constitution of Pakistan and international law. Lack of menstruation care in jails composes a public health hazard and violates women's fundamental human rights.

Sustainable Development Goals and MHM in Prisons

Worldwide Agenda for Sustainable Development offers an important foundation for understanding menstrual hygiene management within prisons. Various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are associated directly and indirectly with menstrual health and sanitation. SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being) prescribe universal health coverage and access to the services of reproductive healthcare, which surround imprisoned women. SDG 5 (Gender Equality) emphasizes the elimination of gender-based discrimination, corroborating that women in unsafe situation such as imprisonment not make them deprived of dignity and fundamental rights. SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) focuses the necessity for hygiene, clean water and the sanitation facilities. In overpopulated Pakistani prisons, where bathrooms are sometimes shared among various convicts and water supply is contrary. Due to which, maintaining menstrual hygiene becomes challenging. Moreover, SDG 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions) emphasizes the requisite of transparent and liable institution in protecting rights, as an aspect in which Pakistan's jail system still remains deficient (United Nation, 2015). This study aligns with SDGs, locating the issue of menstruation hygiene in prisons within framework of social justice and accountability. It highlights that the supervision of imprisoned women in Punjab is not only a local administrative defects but rather an element of comprehensive issue in fulfilling international development and human rights commitments. Lack of proper MHM facilities hampers the advancement of

Pakistan towards these goals and sustain systemic gender inequality. Accordingly, placing the study within the framework of SDG has both national and international importance. It emphasizes that minor rehabilitates such as ensuring coherent access to sanitary pads, clean water and trained female doctors or personnel, which can improve the position of Pakistan in global obligations while improving dignity and welfare of detained women.

Significance of study

This topic is here in focus because the voids between Punjabi Women prisoners reality, HR commitments and legally constructed framework are addressed by the present study and this study is significant. Evidence shows that such implementation is uneven and substandard despite such clear assertion of the gender specific needs of women in detention in the Pakistan Prison Rules 1978. Besides illuminating a neglected part of jail life, the study attends to structural negligence reinforced by administrative inaction and social shame by centring on menstrual hygiene and sanitation facilities, a critically overlooked aspect of women's health.

The outcomes will be significant across multiple dimensions. The report reviews the state's adherence to its own jail regulations and constitutional safeguards as policies—and CEDAW and other international conventions from the legal and governance perspectives. Furthermore, the report details how the inadequate control of menstrual hygiene in filthy overcrowded prisons poses public health risks by increasing the mental stress and health risks of women prisoners. Finally, the report integrates the perception of justice and equity in Pakistan by arguing the women prisoners, as any other women, are entitled to humane and equitable treatment regardless of their detention or conviction.

As part of its global perspective, the report also aligns the community-level issue with the

Sustainable

Development Goals (SDGs). It shows the impacts of detention sanitation failure on the achievement of SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions). The study underscores the fact that safeguarding the health and the well-being of the female incarcerated population is more than a local concern; it is part of the global development and justice framework, thus requiring the transformation of prisons in line with the SDG agenda.

Ultimately this study is impactful because it gives actionable data that can inform awareness initiatives and prison management frameworks, alongside legal changes. This requires out-of-the-box thinking concerning women's health and its budget, as well as trust and fiscal backing from the communities. In doing this, it furthers the academic discussion, advances the conversation on women prison reforms, and holistic female inmate advocacy, arguably the most sidelined portion of humanity.

This study aims to assess the provision of menstrual hygiene and sanitation facilities to Punjabi women prisoners in the context of the Pakistan Prison Rules (PPR) 1978 compliance. Though the Rules provide for the basic minimum to be supplied as sanitary pads, soap, maternal clothes, and requisite medical attention to be given to women prisoners, the prison system is documented and known to be devoid of basic compliance. This study wishes to document the gaps and analyze the denial of these women's rights and the violation of their dignity and health, and the obligations asserted by prison authorities as humanitarian and constitutional duties.

The study illustrates how gaps in surveillance in jails jeopardize both the state-level responsibilities and global development objectives through the lens of the Sustainable

Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 3 (Health and Well-being), SDG 5 (Gender Equity), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice and strong institutions). Besides the systemic focus, the study aims to offer law based recommendations which strengthen compliance to human rights, bolster the gendered rehabilitative reforms of prisons, and guarantee that incarcerated women receive the legal protection and dignities owed to them.

Purpose of Study

Despite the constitutional provisions ensuring equality and the Pakistan Prison Rules from 1978 which outlines the legal and administrative framework of the country and seeks to safeguard female prisoners from discrimination, there is a gap between laws and the actual practice of menstrual hygiene management (MHM). Fulfilling the basic rights of women prisoners, like providing menstrual hygiene and sanitation products, clean water, and private washing facilities, is the subject of continuous human rights and academic research, which highlights the lack of basic sanitary provisions. The cultural stigma around menstruation silence discussions and leads to a plethora of ignored requirements. The gap between the available laws and women's basic rights and hygiene needs exposes insufficient ratification of national and international commitments like CEDAW, the Women's Convention and the Sustainable Development Goals. This undermines the necessity for prison reforms that attend to basic needs of female inmates, focusing on menstruation hygiene.

Research Objectives

To assess the acceptability and availability of menstrual hygiene, facilities for clean water and sanitation provided to women detainees in Punjab, with major focus on accessibility of

sanitary items, water, toilets and privacy as well.

To evaluate the dimensions up to which the jail authorities and administration are in accordance with the PPR 1978 associating the hygiene, health and gender-specific necessities of female detainees.

To evaluate the calibration of jail conditions with SDGS, especially SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 5(Gender Equality), SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice and Strong Institution)

Research Question

To what extent do the menstrual hygiene and health facilities deliver to women detainees in Punjab in accordance with the PPR 1978, and in what way such practice aligns with SDGs associated especially with gender equality, health, sanitation and justice?

Research Hypothesis

H1: Sanitation facilities for menstrual hygiene for women detainees in Punjab are inadequate causing physical and mental health problems.

H2: Jail officials in Punjab don't adhere entirely with the provisions of PPR 1978, pertaining gender-specific health and hygiene.

H3: The commitment of Pakistan to SDGs (especially 3, 5, 6, and 16) are not being met by current condition of MHM and sanitation facilities in Punjab jails.

Literature Review

Although, the legal framework of Pakistan embraces the Pakistan Prison Rules 1978 and assurances of equality and protection of women prisoners from constitution, with undeniable execution of MHM is inadequate. Human rights reports explore deficiencies in the provision of sanitary products, access to clean water and the accessibility of hygienic and private facilities for imprisoned women. Cultural disgrace associated with

menstruation aggravate the suppression of offence, consequently resulted in various undelivered demands. This difference and gaps between policy and practice not only compromises women's dignity and health as well but also shows improper adherence to national legislation and international obligations, including CEDAW and the SDGs (Nagina & Shabid, 2022). Menstruation hygiene is crucial yet dominant issue in Pakistan, intensified by taboos, false information and limited access to hygienic products (Frontiers, 2023). Survey conducted in Islamabad and Rawalpindi indicated that 88.3% of women are aware of menstruation hygiene. 78.7% of women expressed embarrassment while purchasing sanitary products and over half of them encountered monthly health problems. Availability of secure, economical and organic products are associated with enhances satisfaction and respect. These reports explore the necessity of providing menstrual hygiene facilities in unnatural environments such as women prisoners, in accordance with PPR 1978 and the SDGs (Malik, M., & Hashmi, 2023). Menstrual hygiene is fundamental right and public health issue linked with the SDGs 3, 5 and 6. Research conducted in Pakistan suggested widespread dishonor, inadequate awareness and limited access to safe products. Research in Gilgit reported that young girls depend on unsanitary products practices owing to improper Wash facilities and cultural hurdles (Shaikh et al, 2023). These institutional problems are likely aggravated in jails, where female are completely dependent on state. Despite the PPR 1978, the research shows poor execution and enforcement, enhancing concerns over dignity, sanitation and adherence to the international standards (UNODC, 2014; Khan, 2022). In Pakistan, menstrual hygiene is deeply rooted in socio-cultural norms, values and patriarchal practices, mostly articulated as "Customs of our ancestors".

These cultures and norms sustain silence, disgrace and insufficient facilities in the educational institutions, providing females open way to exclusion, absenteeism and adverse health impacts. By enhancing menstrual hygiene necessitates not only the infrastructure but also challenges the cultural taboos, community involvement and educational promotion. Resisting these systemic hurdles is important for ensuring gender parity and attaining comprehensive health and development goals (Mumtaz et al, 2019).

The jail facilities in Punjab elaborate profound systemic issues of overpopulating, improper sanitation, corruption and dishonor for the fundamental rights. In spite of, legal regulations, majority of jails are congested, consequently resulting in prisoners lack of proper sleeping arrangements, sanitation and clean water. Infectious diseases such as HIV, TB and Hepatitis accelerate rapidly due to unsanitary conditions and improper medical care.

The quality of food is deficient, identified by the reports of improper portion sizes, corruption and mismanagement within the supply networks. Women prisoners are more vulnerable because to insufficient facilities, lack of gender sensitive changes and inadequate health care, which threaten their dignity and wellness. Despite lessen reporting of direct sexual harassment owing to gender-isolated facilities, female prisoners constantly encounter the systemic neglect, improper sanitation and restricted access to legal or rehabilitative resources (Shahbaz et al, 2023). Significant number of female detainees are either awaiting trial or serving terms for minor, non-violent offense, enhancing inquires over the equity and justice of the system. The lack and crucial gender-sensitivity changes and facilities encompasses the marginalization of female and their dependent children in prisons.

According to the reports from World Prison Brief and the Human Rights Ministry, Pakistani jail function well below the international standards, providing the prisoners susceptible to bad treatment and neglect. In 2021, 2422 women were imprisoned in detention facilities in Pakistan, mentioning a quick necessity for reform to secure and protect their fundamental rights and facilitate effective rehabilitation. This ignorance and neglect endangers their physical health and emphasizes psychological distress and social humiliation.

Negotiating menstrual hygiene through provision of sanitary products supplies, overreach initiatives and gender-sensitive disciplinary practices is important and crucial as well. Ensuring the fundamental rights would improve prison conditions and enhance the rehabilitation and dignity of the imprisoned women in Pakistan (Hassan et al, 2023). Although the PPR 1978 and the KPK Prison Rules 2018 obligate proper healthcare, nutrition and sanitation in accordance with the international human rights standards, actual enforcement and execution is deficient. The women detainees confront insufficient medical care, poor-quality diet and absence of menstrual hygiene provisions, all of which characterizes their vulnerability and quick recover.

Overpopulating, improper trained personnel and badly effective monitoring emphasizes their situation. To secure the rights of female prisoners, institutional reforms, improved accountability and gender-sensitive punitive practices are needed. In the absence effective and quick innovative and intervention. Female prisoners would constantly endure systemic neglect, so reinforcing the cycles of poor health, inequity and breaches of their fundamental rights (Uzma & Ashraf, 2023). Improper menstruation hygiene importantly effects women's physical, social and mental health. Improper access to hygienic sanitary products and proper facilities mostly results in

reproductive tract infections, UTI and heightened the risk of cervical cancer. Taboos and social stigma linked with menstruation encompasses the problem, resulting in humiliation, distress and reduced self-esteem (Nayab et al, 2025).

Methodology

Qualitative research method is used in this study and conducted in-depth and semi-structured interviews with 13 women who were imprisoned in prison in Rawalpindi. The participants were allowed to explain their experiences with menstrual health using open-ended questions and follow-up inquires thoroughly examined refined topics. To protect their privacy and lessen the coercion, each interview was done in private environment and lasted for about 20-30 minutes. Analysis of Interpretative Phenomenological (IPA) was used to examine the written transcriptions of data in order to uncover both open and hidden meanings.

Research Design

The research focuses on the phenomenological approach to study the experiences of suppressed and marginalized communities. It draws on phenomenology to help understand female inmates' experiences of menstruation during the incarceration period. The focus goes beyond the consequences of menstruation from a mental, emotional, and social perspective, as well as the deeply ingrained sociocultural factors. This research examines the adequacy, or lack thereof, of prison conditions against the international and national legal frameworks and contextualizes the findings with the Pakistan Prison Rules 1978 alongside the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of 2015—specifically 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), 5 (Gender Equality), and 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation).

Sampling and Participants

Thirteen women prisoners, aged from 20 to 50 participated in the investigation. Purposive sampling was used to ensure the involvement of women from different backgrounds, emphasizing both unmarried and married ladies and moms at various stages of their reproductive health, ranging from young adults to towards those undergoing menopause. This diverse variety offered comprehensive study of menstrual health problems throughout different phases of life. Some women were detained for long time period (15-20years) while others were rather on their trial phase or imprisoned for short time period. This prison experience facilitated the identification of prevailing difficulties and different issues linked with age, marital status and length of imprisonment.

Data Collection

In-depth semi-structured interviews were done with women prisoners in Rawalpindi to collect the necessary data for the study. Employing follow-up questions delved deeper into sensitive issues, and open-ended questions allowed participants to express their concerns freely, fostering the sharing of nuanced personal stories. Along with inquiring about the potable water's availability and sanitary facilities, waste disposal services, and other menstrual health behaviors like the use of sanitary pads or whether inmates resorted to cloth and other makeshift substitutes, these areas were also of interest. Participants were asked about the quality of the food served in the jails and its impact on their reproductive and general health. The interviews covered women's experiences of the shame, social isolation, and stigma of menstruation they faced in the prisons. The interviews included descriptions of the coping strategies women employed during their menstrual cycles in highly restricted environments of privacy and resources.

Due to potential coercion or backlash from jail staff, participants were interviewed in private to preserve their confidentiality. Each session lasted between 20-30 minutes, during which both verbal responses and non-verbal cues were documented. To capture and document participants' subtler responses, such as unwillingness, internal suffering, or significant physical movements, field notes were maintained. This approach enriched the data and highlighted the psychological suffering caused by imprisonment. A detailed understanding of the complex issues, especially with regard to menstruation and other hygiene and health concerns, with some observations and field notes about the women inmates was possible through a combination of firsthand narratives and observational notes.

Findings

The prisoners mostly linked the improper nutritional amount of jail food to the issues with their reproductive health, which was the major subject in the interviews. Meals were identified as being dry, hard, repetitive and made up of carbohydrates with little or no protein, fruits, or items high in iron. Young women and juvenile offenders encompassed how this malnutrition led to bad cramps and unpredictable menstrual cycles, resulting in making the menstruation experience more upset. Exhaustion, frustration, irritation and mood swings were among the symptoms of early or premature menopause that women in their late thirties and early forties reported. Many women detainees reported that they experience severe weakness, dizziness and fainting episodes during their periods, while they imputed to chronic starvation and anemia. It showed that how poor diet of prison upset their hormonal balance. Managing the transitions of menopause in prison was challenging for older convicts, particularly 45 years of age and older. Many

explained experiencing prolonged menstrual periods and especially excessive bleedings, which gone untreated because there was no medical support or accessibility at all. None of them mentioned having access to gynecological consultations, iron supplements or any pain killers. There were no any diagnostic services available, despite the fact many women were afraid that they might have any major reproductive problem. These women were forced to suffer in silence as their pains, fatigue and untreated anemia worsened due to lack of medical attention. Their stories and condition were questioning the larger institutions negligence for women's reproductive health necessity, particularly when it comes to aging and menopause.

The availability of sanitary pad was another continual theme. None of the interviews reported that the jail officials provide them such hygienic products or supplies regularly. Majority of them used leftover fabrics and clothes, which they use to wash repeatedly in filthy washrooms without detergent or soap. Though this practice which is born out of necessity had caused health complications and issues such as UTI, skin rashes, bad odors, vaginal irritation and fungus. Their dependence on such hazardous alternative shows the seriousness of menstrual poverty inside such correctional facilities. Moreover, the participants mostly explained feeling humiliation when they ask for sanitary products or access to restrooms. A major portion of them related how the male jail staff neglected or mocked their appeals. Female's distress and respect were undermined when the guards in various situation flatly refused them the access to restrooms during any emergencies. According to women, these situations were extremely demeaning and were expressive of large number of institutionalized gender insensitivity culture. Moreover, violation of fundamental rights of female prisoners, this kind of dishonor

upholds the hurdles to period management that are both safe and respectable as well.

One of the biggest barriers to MHM was the jail's physical infrastructure. The restrooms of jail in Rawalpindi was identifies as being unclean, overpopulated and lack of privacy. Women complained of lengthy sentences to use the facilities, which were even worse by regular shortage of water. Many of them described the feeling of being ashamed and humiliated after being made to wash the blood-stained clothes in fronts of others. Prisoners were forced to manage the menstrual waste in unsafe and undignified way because lack of effective waste disposal facilities, which made the issue worse.

These circumstances mad them women deprived of their privacy and self-respect, which not only affected their physical hygiene but also caused theme emotional distress. Women mentioned significant emotional distress and psychological cost related to menstruation in jail, in addition to health issues. Feelings of loneliness, neglect and shame were not just seen but were dominant over them. Most of the women reported depressive symptoms associated with their incapacity to manage their periods with dignity. Old age women spoke of feeling abandoned and excluded by the institution during menopause, while younger detainees were concerned about the long-term effects of irregular menstrual cycle on their fertility. Their distress was encompassed by the absence of therapeutic therapies, psychological support and counseling. Thereby, menstruation evolved from biological phenomenon to a cause of long-lasting psychological distress, emphasizing general difficulties linked with imprisonment.

Figure1: Findings from Interviews**Data Analysis**

To evaluate the data, the researcher employed IPA, or Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis, which is a qualitative method allowing the researcher to capture each participant's comments and interpret the “within the quotes” deeper meanings of their experiences. This approach was useful in studying delicate subjects such as menstruation in prisons, areas often fraught with institutional neglect, the burden of shame, and silence that erases women’s voices. Through painstaking coding, classification, and interpretation, five overarching themes that encapsulated prisoners' struggles with menstrual health emerged.

The first topic, hormonal imbalance and nutritional deficiency, illustrated the repercussions of inadequate diets on women's reproductive health. For older incarcerated women, malnutrition, defined as insufficient protein, iron, and an abundance of carbohydrates, led to disrupted menstrual cycles, severe cramps, dizziness, and early

menopausal

symptoms. This relationship between nutritional intake and reproductive health underscores the impact insufficient nutrition has on incarcerated women’s overall menstrual health.

The second theme “not having access to sanitary pads and relying on dangerous alternatives,” highlighted there was no access to sanitary pads and there was no access to sanitary pads and women had to resort to unsafe alternatives. None of the women surveyed claimed to have received sanitary pads, which meant women were forced to rely on pieces of clothing or fabric that were washed far too infrequently. This not only added to the collection of illnesses and infections a woman faced, not to mention having to deal with rashes and the putrid smell, but also contributed to dehumanizing women by forcing them to conceal blood-soaked clothes to avoid the ‘mockery’ of having menstruated.

The third theme addressed health care gaps and health risks— revealed gaps within the prison— highlighted the gaps within the prison healthcare system as a crucial weak point. For participants suffering from menstrual and reproductive health disorders, the concern gynecological and diagnostic services as well as medicines were not accessible. Women suffering from anemia, excessive menstrual bleeding, and other gynecological disorders were not receiving any type of medical treatment. A good number of the prisoners experienced worrying health problems because they were not given several medications such as analgesics, iron tablets, and routine examinations.

Criminal neglect and gender insensitivity— the final and fifth theme— showed how women’s reproductive health issues in jails and prisons are systematically ignored. Reported accounts of male guards not only ridiculing requests for napkins and restroom access, but also not caring about these

matters, reflect a serious absence of gender awareness. The fourth theme, psychological pressure and social stigma, illustrated how the process of menstruation within the prisons is not only physically painful, but also mentally and emotionally tormenting. During this difficult time, women described themselves as deeply ashamed, humiliated, and alone, especially having to deal with menstruation.

The situation was aggravated by the presence of unsanitary and congested sanitary facilities, as well as a complete absence of waste disposal for accumulated refuse. All of the testimonies together, however, showed a complete failure to meet women's sanitary concerns, which violates human rights, dignity, and a sensible humane system of managing the prison.

The collective outcome reveals with clarity the interplay of inadequate care, lack of appropriate spatial design, insensitivity to women's needs, and systemic bias, which together compromise the menstrual health and welfare of detained women, as well as the need for immediate attention to jail design that incorporates a gender-sensitive framework and views menstruation as a fundamental health and human right.

Ethical Consideration

As the topic is so fragile, strict moral guidelines were followed. To ensure confidentiality, participants were given pseudonyms. In light of literacy barriers, verbal informed permission and instructions were obtained. Informed permission also aligns with the willingness to participate guidelines for these women which meant that women were able to stop participating at any time without any consequences. To protect the participants from any potential reprisals from prison staff, the interviews were conducted privately. The researcher empathized with the participants and respected their culture. Conversations about menstruation, menopause, and reproductive

health were held with due care to avoid causing further trauma.

Discussion

The findings of the study illustrate the intersection of social neglect, health, and gender, which highlight the absence of proper attention to reproduction and menstruation needs of women in Pakistani jails. The analysis also showcases 'insufficient medical support,' 'psychological distress,' and 'institutional neglect' et al. which exhibit women's health neglect in a more holistic sense, revealing profound patriarchy structures of social inequality and gender-based discrimination.

The overlooked prison diet explicitly manifests the health inequality phenomenon within correctional facilities, which for a long time showed that incarcerated people face malnutrition to a great degree. With women, the problem is worse since malnutrition affects reproductive health, leading to abnormal cycles, painful cramps, and early menopause. And in the case of women, food in jails is not only to be eaten for surviving, but also for controlling the menstrual health. With menstruation, the lack of nutrition contributes to the increase of ill health, making imprisoned women more vulnerable to long-term diseases and reproductive health problems.

Evidently, the lack of sanitary items is becoming a global concern, particularly with regards to research on women in prisons. In Rawalpindi, menstrual poverty impacts women's health and their dignity while also causing disruption to their hygiene. The reliance on makeshift gowns, which are washed in filthy conditions, increases the risk of infections, dermatitis, and humiliation. Such evidence asserts the feminist viewpoint that not providing menstrual hygiene products is a violation of basic human rights, more so in a prison situation where women are cut off

from the option to freely fetch these necessities.

“Systematic incompetence” comes to mind when describing the lack of reproductive health services and gynecological care. The absence of care for conditions like anemia or excessive bleeding, coupled with the lack of basic medications, portrays a prison as a place where people lose the basic human freedom and in return receive no health care. Such descriptions form the groundwork of broader arguments that the prison system is designed to operate without human considerations. The absence of any form of response to this gap not only reflects the absence of resources but also poorly managed governance, where women’s health is totally ignored and buried under the corrective ideology.

Why did women endure so much suffering over a normal biological process? Menstrual cycles bring about feelings of emotional pain and a unique anxiety about possibly becoming barren. For social and psychological reasons, women prefer to bottle their distress away. The absence of physical privacy and the arrogant attitude of prison staff causes social seclusion which intensifies psychological tension and torment. Interpretive Phenomenological Studies focusing women’s subjective experiences, self-imposed interpretation related to the meaning they attribute to their experiences, aggrieves and disquiets women.

Neglect of women’s biologically associated needs within institutional frameworks focuses on a lack of compassion for women’s health. The act of ignoring sanitary requirements such as disposal of used pads signifies a male-dominated approach and lack of basic sensitivity and consideration for women in prisons. This tells us that there seems to be a cultural and institutional invisibility regarding women’s reproductive health as integral to their human rights. Such actions shift menstruation from being a biological, natural process to a tool for institutional control. Such

actions highlight a critical deficiency of the government while serving feminine rights whilst guaranteeing privacy, dignity, and equality.

Based on our findings, menstrual healthcare in jails in Pakistan goes beyond being a mere health issue; it concerns dignity, human rights, and socio-cultural and gender justice. The inequities in reproductive healthcare access in prison settings exacerbate inequities in women’s lives, in and beyond the prison walls. These challenges can be resolved by improving the basic needs of nutrition, sanitation, health services, and gender-sensitive policy. These changes enhance the conditions of imprisonment while simultaneously meeting internationally sanctioned human rights obligations on primary healthcare under the SDGs, particularly 3 and 5.

Conclusion

The focus of this investigation highlights the neglect of reproductive health in the context of healthcare within the carceral system of Pakistani prisons, particularly in terms of malnutrition, ‘healthcare neglect’, psychological strain, over-incarceration, institutional neglect, and their interwoven misogynistic neglect of women’s health. From the accounts of women prisoners in Rawalpindi, one can see that menstruation for them is an experience of the systemic oppression and an inhumane suffering that they have to live through.

The results shed light on the areas of healthcare and menstruation health technology for incarcerated women who lack the appropriate healthcare system. To ignore the women’s healthcare system “as women and socio-economically as a part of the society structure” makes the matter of health and justice, besides the healthcare system of the women which is inhuman, an attempt of socio-economic inequality and gender violence in a worsening form. Hence,

women's healthcare challenges require policy-based and evidence-based multidisciplinary frameworks which are gender sensitive.

The findings suggest that the enhancement of the conditions of women in municipal jail does not work as a mere substitution strategy. If the wellbeing justice of resources allocation is the concern, women's health, more importantly menstruation hygiene and sanitation, lies beyond health justice, and breaches a basic human right. Addressing these issues not only would diminish the sufferings of imprisoned women but also would depict Pakistan as a country which has policies and practices for human rights and gender justice.

Recommendations

The results show that female prisoners' reproductive health needs immediate and continuous care. The ignoring of menstruation cares not only endangers the health of incarcerated women. It also represents a violation of pivotal human rights. Hence, the following suggestions are made to improve the newly identified issues alongside nutrition, and also menstruation related care – healthcare, policy, and facility management.

The correctional facility administrators should guarantee the correctional diet fulfills the women of reproductive age's health and diet needs alongside providing adequate and nutritious food. A balanced diet that contains iron-rich foods is crucial to mitigate anemia and enhances reproductive health. These gaps for better prison food supervision could be filled with cooperation and partnerships with the health ministries and NGOs.

Menstrual hygiene should and must be considered as a basic human right. It is the responsibility of the correctional facility authorities to guarantee the provision of adequate menstruation hygiene products. As a consequence, women should receive sanitary waste bins which are private and clean for the

utilization and disposal of these products. Allocating funds to women hygiene and menstrual care for women in prison alleviates the sporadic donation-reliance situation.

Access to healthcare, especially reproductive health, should be improved in prison institutions. This includes hiring qualified female healthcare practitioners, having gynecological services, routine check-ups, and early management of menstruation issues such as menorrhagia, infections, and anemia. Mobile health units or temporary medical camps can be established for areas with no permanent healthcare facilities.

Mental health support in prisons should be a priority to help cope with the silence, neglect, and lack of privacy restrooms which cause the deepest sorts of emotional pain. Programs aimed at counseling, peer support, and public awareness can help reduce the feeling of shame and help the women to take charge of their reproductive health.

All prison staff should receive gender-sensitive instruction which includes privacy, human rights, and the consideration of women's biological needs. Specifically, male guards should be trained on how to be non-discriminatory and non-ridiculing. Women will be able to report neglect or abuse through the established grievance redressed systems without fear of backlash.

In any case, compliance with SDG 3, Good Health and Well-being and SDG 5, Gender Equality are obligations that must be fulfilled by Pakistan. Policies at the level of the prison system must be based on the principles of social justice which balance the dignity and the health of women. Collaboration with foreign institutions, and bodies concerned with human rights, enhances the level of accountability and ensures that the required changes are effectively and efficiently implemented.

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